

An overview on the sorption of 3d and 4f metal ions on phenolic resins

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Abstract : Synthesis of benzophenone based phenolic resins and study of its ion exchange efficiency using different electrolytes, pH, time and concentrations.

Keywords : Resins, ion-exchange, adsorption, metal ions.

Introduction

Mineral processing and metal finishing industries produce large amount of waste effluents containing toxic elements such as chromium, zinc, cadmium, copper, nickel and other toxic elements¹. Metal ions are non-biodegradable in nature, therefore, their intake beyond certain level is toxic². Copper is both vital and toxic for many biological systems³. The increasing stringent environmental regulations and enforcement of discharge limits require effective decontamination and purification method. From an analytical point of view, it is known that solid phase extraction (SPE) is an attractive technique based on use of sorbent that retains metal ions. The ions are eluted from the sorbent using a suitable eluent. Preconcentration method is widely accepted technique for monitoring low concentration of metal ions.

Numerous methods have been described for effective separation and preconcentration; procedures based on ion exchange^{4,5}, solvent extraction⁶⁻⁸ and SPE⁹⁻¹³ are amongst them. Chelate-forming selected resins¹⁴⁻¹⁷ have found numerous applications for the separation and monitoring of heavy metals including lanthanides from their aqueous solutions¹⁸⁻²⁰. The use of chelating resins for separation or removal of metal ions is the method of choice due to its high separation efficiency, good reproducibility

of retention parameters and simplicity²¹⁻²⁴. Considerable efforts have been made for improvement, economization and optimization of the chelating properties of ion-exchange resins^{25,26}. Chelating ion-exchange resins have specific chelating groups which are extensively useful in separation and preconcentration of metal ions²⁷⁻³⁰. Vernon³¹ has summarized the desirable properties of a chelating polymer which includes its high capacity and appropriate selectivity. Polymeric resins which possess chelating properties are found to be more selective by nature^{32,33} as compared to other conventional techniques^{34,35} to remove metal ions. The SPE methods using molecular imprinted polymers are the most useful methods for separation and preconcentration of trace metals^{36,37}. Molecular imprinting is a methodology for the introduction of selective recognition sites into highly cross-linked polymeric matrices via the template-directed assembly of functionalized monomers into a polymer network³⁸⁻⁴⁰.

The chelate forming polymeric ligands are characterized by reactive functional groups containing O, N, S and P donor atoms and capable of coordinating to different metal ions and these aspects have been extensively studied⁴¹⁻⁴⁷. Chelate forming polymers having multidentate coordination sites are known to form complexes with metal

ions readily⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. In a polymer matrix, they are expected to show affinity and selectivity towards the metal ions at an appropriate pH. This led to synthesize chelating resins, which have affinity for the metal ions at appropriate pH⁵¹⁻⁵⁴.

The phenolic resins are playing a vital role in automobile, electrical and appliance industries⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷.

Principle of ion-exchange process

Ion exchange is a process in which mobile ions from an external solution are exchanged for ions that are electrostatically bound to the functional groups contained within a solid matrix. When the functional groups are negatively charged the exchange will involve cations and when they are positively charged they involve anions.

Table 1. pK values for the most common functional groups of organic ion exchangers

Cation exchangers		Anion exchangers	
Functional group	pK _a	Functional group	pK _b
-SO ₃ H (strong acidic)	1-2	≡N ⁺ (strong basic)	1-2
-PO ₃ H ₂	2-5	=N	4-6
-COOH	4-6	=NH	6-8
-OH (weak acidic)	9-10	-NH ₂ (weak basic)	8-10

Depending on type of the functional group, ion exchangers can be divided into several types viz. strong acidic, strong basic, weak acidic and weak basic. In Table 1 the negative logarithm of the dissociation constant (pK) is given for different functional groups. Ion exchangers containing sulpho-, phospho-acidic groups and those containing tetraammonium basic groups are strong acidic and strong basic exchangers, respectively. Whereas those containing phenolic and primary amino groups are weak acidic and weak basic exchangers, respectively. Exchanger with carboxy groups and tertiary amino groups takes a medium position between strong and weak acidic and basic exchangers, respectively. To achieve the removal of both positively and negatively charged ions from solution, a mixture of cation and anion resins in a mixed bed system is often used, for example, in case of NaCl solution the ion exchange process will be :

Since H₂O is only weakly dissociated, the adsorption reaction is proceeding in the right hand side of the equation.

Ion exchange equilibrium, selectivity, sorption and limitations :

Ion exchange equilibrium can be described by any of the following term :

- The ion exchange isotherm,
- The separation factor,
- The selectivity coefficient,
- The thermodynamic equilibrium constant and
- The distribution coefficient.

These terms are common and well-known in ion-exchange study⁵⁸. It should be noted that selectivity coefficients are not constant and may vary with the experimental conditions. In case of cationic organic ion exchange resins at low concentrations and the temperatures normally encountered in waste processing, the affinity typically increases with (a) an increasing charge on the exchanging cation and (b) an increasing atomic number (decreasing hydrated ionic radii) of the exchanging cation; for example :

(Li⁺ is an exception, owing to its high hydration energy)

For anions a typical series is as follows :

Changes in physical parameters as well as in concentration of functional groups affect the distribution coefficient and the driving force for the ion exchange process. High values of the distribution coefficient are always desirable.

Sorption is a separation process involving two phases between which certain components can become differentially distributed. There are three types of sorption, classified according to the type of bonding involved.

(a) Physical sorption : There is no exchange of electrons in physical sorption, rather intermolecular attractions occur between 'valency happy' sites and are therefore, independent of the electronic properties of the molecules involved. The heat of adsorption or activation energy is low in physical sorption.

(b) Chemical sorption : Chemical sorption or chemisorption involves an exchange of electrons between specific surface sites and solute molecules, which results in the formation of a chemical bond. Such a bond is more

stable at higher temperatures and therefore, the chemisorption is stronger adsorption than physical adsorption.

(c) Electrostatic sorption (ion exchange) : This term is reserved for columbic attractive forces between ions and charged functional groups and is more commonly classified as ion exchange.

In addition to the ion exchangers, ion exchange materials can also act as sorbents. When they are in contact with an electrolyte solution, the dissolved ions are concentrated on both the surface and in the pores of the ion exchange media. In a solution of weak electrolytes or non-electrolytes, sorption by ion exchangers is similar to that of non-ionic adsorbents. In a solution of strong electrolytes sorption equilibrium results, owing to the electrostatic attraction between the ions in solution and the fixed ionic groups on the ion exchange media.

Certain characteristics of ion exchange materials and processes limit their applicability and efficiency. When used as a packed bed in a column, the complete removal of a specific metal ion is not normally possible, owing to leakage or breakthrough. This will cause the metal ions to pass through without being captured. In a properly designed system this breakthrough may be very low, but will still be present.

In batch process, inadequate mixing will also limit the effectiveness of the ion exchange material. The total concentration of dissolved salts in solution must generally be below (< 1 g/L). At high concentrations the exchange potentials for ions diminish and there is more competition for the available exchange sites between desired ions and the undesired ions. However, for specifically developed ion exchangers (usually inorganic) the tolerance for dissolved salts can be very high (e.g. up to 240 g/L⁵⁹).

Ion-exchange materials

A wide range of materials is available for the ion exchange treatment of metal ions in aqueous solution in a variety of forms, have wide difference in their chemical and physical properties. It can be naturally occurring or synthetic materials. Ion exchange materials can be categorized according to their suitability for different applications.

Naturally occurring inorganic, organic and modified ion-exchangers :

Many natural mineral compounds, such as clays (e.g. bentonite, kaolinite and illite), vermiculite and zeolites

(e.g. analcites, chabazite, sodalite and clinoptilolite) exhibit ion exchange properties. Natural zeolites were the first materials to be used in ion exchange processes. Clay materials are often employed as backfill or buffer materials for radioactive waste disposal sites because of their ion exchange properties, low permeability and easy workability. Clays can also be used in batch ion exchange processes but are not generally suited to column operation because their physical properties restrict the flow through the bed⁶⁰.

A large number of organic materials exhibit ion exchange properties; these include polysaccharides (such as cellulose, straw and peat), proteins (such as casein, keratin and collagen) and carbonaceous materials (such as charcoals, lignites and coals). Of these, only charcoals, coal, lignite and peat are used commercially. Although they exhibit a very low ion exchange capacity compared with synthetic ion-exchangers.

Some naturally occurring organic ion-exchangers are modified to improve ion-exchange capacity by chemical and/or thermal treatment^{61,62}.

Synthetic inorganic and organic ion-exchangers :

Synthetic ion exchangers are produced by preparing new chemical compounds with desired physical and chemical properties. They can be used on inorganic (mineral) or organic material (generally polymer). Zeolites were largely used for removal of metal ions from solution⁶³⁻⁶⁸. However, synthetic zeolites can be engineered with a wide variety of chemical properties, pore size and thermally high stable. Titanates and hydrous titanium oxide are known to be highly selective exchangers for strontium⁶⁹⁻⁷². It is a highly effective exchanger in an alkaline solution (i.e. for pH > 9)⁷³. These exchangers have a high selectivity both for cesium and strontium⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶. Insoluble transition metal hexacyanoferrates were found suitable for removing some heavy metals from alkaline reprocessing waste containing a high concentration of sodium salts^{78,79}. A freshly precipitated cupric hexacyanoferrate are also used for the removal of cesium from aqueous solution^{80,81}.

The largest group of ion exchangers available today are synthetic organic resins in a powdered (5–150 μm) or bead (0.5–2 mm diameter) form. The framework or matrix, of the resins is a flexible random network of hydrocarbon chains. This matrix carries fixed ionic charges at various locations. The degree of cross-linking of resin determines the mesh width of the matrix, swelling abi-

lity, movement of mobile ions, hardness and mechanical durability.

The most common form of ion exchange resin is based on a copolymer of styrene and divinylbenzene. Resin, with low divinylbenzene content are soft and gelatinous and swell strongly in solvent. Fixed ionic groups are introduced into resin matrix to produce an ion-exchanger, this introduced group then become the mobile or counter ion which can be replaced by a treatment with a solution containing another cation. Anion exchangers can be produced by creating $-NH_3^+$ or $-N_2^+$ functional groups on the matrix with OH^- , Cl^- or other anions as the counter ion.

Phenol-formaldehyde condensation products, with the phenolic ($-OH$) groups as the fixed ionic groups, are very weak acid exchangers. Sulphonation of phenol prior to polymerization can be used to increase the acid strength. Phenolsulphonic acid resins are bifunctional with both strong acid $-SO_3H$ and weak acid $-OH$ groups included. A resorcinol-formaldehyde polycondensation resin was recently developed for removal of heavy metal from alkaline reprocessing waste⁸²⁻⁸⁴. Incorporation of iminodiacetic acid functional group in the phenolic polymer gives the additional property for uptake of metal ion by chelation^{85,86}.

Ion-exchange techniques

Ion exchange processes can be implemented in a variety of ways, but batch and column operations are widely accepted techniques.

Batch operation is the simplest method for operating an ion exchange process. It can be used with either organic or inorganic media and it does not require sophisticated equipment and can be carried out on any scale at ambient temperatures and pressures. A measured quantity of the ion exchange medium is mixed with the liquid waste in a suitable container. The amount of media required and the rate of exchange can be determined using the following equation :

$$K_d = (DF - 1) \times V/m$$

where, K_d = measured distribution coefficient; DF = required decontamination factor; V = volume of liquid to be purified and, m = amount of the ion exchange medium needed to reach the required decontamination factor.

The mixture is allowed to equilibrate for a specified time either with or without stirring. At the end, the ion exchange medium is removed from the liquid using conventional separation techniques such as decantation, filtration or centrifugation. The treatment can be repeated as required by adding further ion exchange media. Either powdered or bead type media can be used in batch processing. Bead media is easier to remove by filtration, but powdered media is providing larger surface area for contact between the liquid and the media, resulting in faster sorption kinetics and therefore, time required for reaction is short.

While in column operation, the most common use of ion exchange media is as packed bed in vessels or columns. The ion exchange medium is enclosed inside a steel pressure vessel with an engineered inlet, outlet and flow distribution system to allow liquid to percolate through the bed of the medium at a controlled flow rate. Columns are generally used with bead type ion exchange media and can be constructed in a wide variety of sizes and materials to meet the requirements of the system. The low porosity of bed powdered material restricts their use to thin layers, usually as a 'pre-coat' on a filter medium.

Column systems can be configured for single bed operation systems or mixed bed systems, in which cation and anion media are mixed together in a suitable proportion (usually equal portions). However, moving bed and pulsed bed systems can provide a more uniform liquid product and can have a lower media inventory than column systems. Moving bed and pulsed bed systems are also more tolerant to particulates in the liquid.

Synthesed phenolic resins and its ion-exchange study

Benzophenone based phenolic resins and ion-exchange characteristic :

Benzophenone based chelating phenolic resins were synthesized by polycondensation of 2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone with different diols, such as ethylene glycol (EG), propylene glycol (PG), 1,3-propane diol (1,3-PD), 1,3-butane diol (1,3-BD) and 1,4-butane diol (1,4-BD), in presence of acid catalyst. Substituted at position 4 of 2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone has been carried out by converting $-OH$ to $-OCH_3$, $-OC_4H_9$ etc. Mixture of 2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone and respective diol was condensed in presence of polyphosphoric acid as a catalyst at

suitable temperature for appropriate time. The product obtained was purified by washing with water followed by methanol to remove unreacted acid and monomer⁸⁶. This general procedure was used for the synthesis of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone - diol resins, 2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone - diol resins^{87,88}.

Here the benzophenone moieties are linked through 3 and 5 positions of the aromatic ring with respective diols. The ethylene glycol form $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$, propylene glycol form $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-\text{CH}_2-$, 1,3-propane diol form $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$, 1,3-butane diol and 1,4-butane diol forms $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ bridges respectively.

sized in similar manner.

The study of '3d' transition and '4f' inner transition metal ions adsorption with different synthesized benzophenone based phenolic resins was carried out. All the benzophenone based resins possess $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups as chelating sites, which forms coordinated covalent bonds with metal ions. Not only ion-exchange techniques and physical parameters but structure and nature of the resin are important factors, which affect the sorption of the metal ions. 2,4-Dihydroxy benzophenone - diol resin shows maximum efficiency for binding with transition as well as inner transition metal ions in compared to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone - diol and

Monomer	Bridging groups (-X-)	Resin

Benzophenone based phenolic resins with different bridging groups were synthesized using dichloro methane (DCM), 1,2-dichloro ethane (DCE) etc. The resin was synthesized by polycondensation of 2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone and 1,2-dichloro methane. Finely powdered anhydrous aluminum chloride was added in the above mixture. The reaction mixture was refluxed at appropriate temperature and time. The obtained product was purified by washing with hot 10% methanol to remove unreacted monomer. The resins of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone with dichloro methane, 1,2-dichloro ethane etc. were synthe-

2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone - diol resins. This is because of bigger size of $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9$ than phenolic $-\text{OH}$ at 4th position of resins causes steric hindrance in adsorption of metal ions. The acidity of phenolic $-\text{OH}$ group is decreases due to etherification. The resin possesses $-\text{OH}$ group is having highest efficiency than resin possesses $-\text{OCH}_3$ or $-\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9$ groups. The order of efficiency of the functional groups is given as follows :

The phenolic resin possess $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ in its backbone have highest metal binding capacity for transition as well

as inner transition metal ions. The increase in $-CH_2-$ group in the bridge, the metal binding capacity of resin decreases step by step. This is because the space between two phenolic moieties is increased. This reduces the metal binding efficiency due to unstable complexation. Thus amongst all studied phenolic resins, ion-exchange capacity and the efficiency of synthesized benzophenone based phenolic resins have been observed as shown below :

2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone > 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone > 2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone

Metal adsorption capacity of benzophenone based resins also depends on different diols which forms bridge between two substituted benzophenone monomers. The rate at which ions adsorbed under given conditions decreases as one passes from :

B-DCM > B-DCE \approx B-ED > B-PD > B-1,4-BD > B-PG > B-1,3-BD

where, B = substituted benzophenone moiety.

Metal adsorption by batch equilibration method :

The chelating behaviour of synthesized phenolic resins for lanthanides and transition metal ions was determined by the batch equilibrium technique. The fine resin powder sample was dried in vacuum at 60 °C for 24 h. The finely powdered dried resin samples were used for metal ion adsorption. Duplicate experiments involving 0.50 g of dry, 300 mesh size resin samples were equilibrated with 15.0 mL of acetate-acetic acid buffer solution of pH 7.0 ionic strength of 0.10 M (using sodium perchlorate) for 2 h. To this mixture, 2.0 mL of 0.1 M metal ion solution was added. After being shaken for 24 h at 30 °C, the mixture was filtered and metal content remaining in the filtrate was determined by complexometric titration using standard Na_2EDTA solution with appropriate indicator⁸⁹.

(a) To investigate the effect of different electrolytes at various concentrations on metal ion uptake, experiments were carried out with a fixed contact time of 24 h, at 30 °C and pH 5.6 using $NaNO_3$, $NaCl$, Na_2SO_4 and $NaClO_4$ electrolytes at different concentrations.

(b) Similar experiments were also carried out in pH range 3.0 and 5.5 for a fixed contact time of 24 h at ionic strength of 0.1 M $NaNO_3$ electrolyte solution.

(c) The selectivity of resin for lanthanides and transition metal ions was examined under similar experimental conditions where the contact time was varied from 1 to 24 h at 30 °C after being equilibrated with distilled water.

(d) Similar experiments were carried out for different concentrations of metal ion for a fixed contact time at particular ionic strength of 0.1 M $NaNO_3$ electrolyte solution.

Influence of an electrolyte, pH, time and metal ion concentrations on uptake of metal ions :

The effect of nature and concentrations of an electrolyte solution was investigated by determining the metal ion adsorbed by resin at room temperature. The electrolytes $NaNO_3$, $NaCl$, Na_2SO_4 and $NaClO_4$ were used.

All experiments were carried out with 50 mg of the resin samples under specified conditions, in presence of various concentrations of electrolytes under study. The 50 mg of the resin sample was stirred in each of the following four solutions for 24 h.

Set	:	I	II	III	IV
Concentration	:	0.05 M	0.1 M	0.5 M	1.0 M

0.1 M solution of metal ion (2 mL) was added to each of the above solutions. The pH of the mixed solution was adjusted to the given value by adding required amount of aqueous acid or alkali. After 24 h the content of each filtrate and washings were collected. The metal ion in solution was estimated using complexometric method with standard Na_2EDTA .

The study reveals that, the extent of Ln^{3+} ions uptake by resin increases with increase in the concentration of NO_3^- , ClO_4^- and Cl^- and decreases with an increase in concentration of SO_4^{2-} . This may be due to the higher charge and bigger size of the sulphate ion, in addition, other factors are also responsible for the behavior of SO_4^{2-} ion. Therefore, the influence of NO_3^- , ClO_4^- and Cl^- is less, on the position of metal chelates at equilibrium state that does SO_4^{2-} .

It is observed that in presence of NO_3^- , Cl^- and ClO_4^- ions good results are obtained for all metal ions. While SO_4^{2-} ion is not found suitable for maintaining high strength of solution in the exchange study. The Cl^- ion has a tendency to form complexes with many metal ions⁹⁰.

In the ion-exchange study all the relevant experiments were carried out using NaNO_3 , as an electrolyte to maintain constant ionic strength of the solution. The manner of sorption of metal ions by benzophenone based resins in presence of different electrolyte solutions with different pH is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Metal ion uptake as a function of electrolyte concentrations.

The binding capacity of resin for lanthanide and transition metal ions was studied in 1.0 M NaNO_3 (40 mL) solution within the pH range 3.0 to 6.0 under continuous shaking for a fixed contact time of 24 h at 30 °C.

The resin sample (50 mg) was suspended in the electrolyte solution and pH of the suspension was adjusted to required value by addition of either 0.1 M HNO_3 or 0.1 M NaOH solution. To this, metal solution 0.1 M metal nitrate (2 mL) was added and the pH of the medium was adjusted to the desired value. The content was mechanically stirred for 24 h, filtrated and washed with distilled water. This experiment was performed using 0.1 M metal nitrate solution of transition and lanthanide metal ions at the pH values 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0 and 5.5.

Typical pH-binding capacity profile for the resin indicates that, at lower pH values (< pH 6) protonation of chelating group takes place, complexation available with ligands is reduced and hence the percentage uptake decreases. At higher pH values (> pH 6) deprotonation of coordination resin takes place and hence, the absence of the competition between metal ions and protons for lone pair of electrons is observed. Thus, the percentage of metal ions uptake increases through the formation of stable polymer-metal complexes⁹¹. It is found that the relative amount of metal ion uptake by the resin increases with increase in pH of the medium⁹²⁻⁹⁴. Thus maximum uptake of metal ion occurs at pH = 5.5. The pH effect on

adsorption of metal ion by benzophenone based resins is shown in Fig. 2 as an example.

Fig. 2. Metal ion uptake as a function of pH of the medium.

The distribution ratio K_D of metal ions between the resin phase (solid) and aqueous phase (liquid) is estimated at optimum pH using 1.0 M NaNO_3 solution. The experiments were carried out from 3.0 to 5.5 pH. Distribution ratio K_D (the concentration of metal ion in the adsorbed form on the resin phase divided by concentration of metal ion in solution phase) has been calculated using following equation.

$$K_D = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion adsorbed by resin}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution}} \times \frac{\text{Volume of solution}}{\text{Weight of resin}}$$

The effect of pH on the amount of metal ions distributed between two phases can be explained. It can be seen that the distribution ratio increases for lanthanide and transition metal ions as the pH of the medium increase. It is found that the value of distribution ratio for given pH depends upon the nature of the polymeric ligand (resin) as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Distribution ratio (K_D) of metal ion as a function of pH.

In this technique, a 0.50 g of dry 300 mesh sample of the resin was preconditioned by allowing the resin to equilibrate for 2 h with the buffer solution at pH 6.0 before the ion-exchange experiment. The ion-exchange experiments were performed at 30 °C under continuous shaking as a function of constant contact time from 1 to 24 h.

The study shows that the uptake of metal ion increases with time until it reaches a steady state. It is assumed that at 30 °C and under given conditions, the state of equilibrium is established in 24 h. The rate of metal ion uptake is expressed as percentage of the attainment at state of equilibrium. The uptake of metal ion by the resin increases with increase in initial metal ion concentration and reaches a plateau at higher concentration⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷. The uptake of metal ions by the resin involves either chelation or ion-exchange or both. Ion-exchange behaviour of metal ion by benzophenone based resin as a function of time is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Metal ion uptake as a function of time.

The effect of metal ion concentration on uptake behaviour of the different synthesized resins was studied in the concentration range 250–2000 mg per 10 mL of the metal ion. Increasing the concentration of metal ion enhanced the percentage of loading. However, a leveling effect was noticed at higher concentration because of saturation of available coordination sites. Tikhomirova *et al.*⁹⁸ have observed a similar trend. The adsorption coefficient K_{ad} of the resin for the adsorption of transition and lanthanide metal ions was computed from Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

$$\log (x/m) = \log K_{ad} \times 1/nx (\log c)$$

where, c = initial concentration of the metal ion in mmole; m = weight of the resin in mg; x = quantity of

the metal ion adsorbed by the resin in the mmole; n = constant.

From the results, it is observed that high K_{ad} values indicate that, the saturation time for adsorption of metal ion is attained quickly. The Luo and coworkers have reported that the slow adsorption rate of metal ions is due to low K_{ad} values⁹⁹. The new benzophenone based resin with different diols, dichloro alkenes and its chelating properties with lanthanides and transition metal ions have additive values in the present ion-exchange material and processes. Chelation properties of the synthesized resins are influenced by the medium, pH of the solution, nature and concentrations of the electrolyte solution.

Future trends

Looking to the present results in case of 2,4-dihydroxy benzophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-butoxy benzophenone may be proved effective and efficient ion-exchange resins with appropriate physical parameters such as pH, electrolytes, concentration, time etc.

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